

Research Article

A new combination in *Diplazium* (Athyriaceae)

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Abstract: A new combination is proposed here for *Callipteris stolzei* Pacheco & R.C.Moran under the genus *Diplazium* Sw. as *D. stolzei* (Pacheco & R.C.Moran) R.Kr.Singh, V.K.Rawat & Sanjeet Kumar.

Keywords: *Callipteris stolzei*, Endemic, Ecuador

Introduction

The cosmopolitan genus *Diplazium* Sw. consists of about 470 species (POWO, 2025). In Ecuador, the genus is represented by about 76 species, namely *D. aberrans* Maxon & C.V.Morton, *D. alienum* (Mett.) Hieron., *D. ambiguum* Raddi, *D. andinum* (Pacheco & R.C.Moran) M.Kessler & A.R.Sm., *D. angulosum* C.Chr., *D. avitaguense* Hieron., *D. bicolor* Stolze, *D. bombonasae* Rosenst., *D. caracasenum* (Willd.) Kunze ex T.Moore, *D. celtidifolium* Kunze, *D. centripetale* (Baker) Maxon, *D. ceratolepis* (Christ) Christ, *D. chimboanum* (Sodirol) C.Chr., *D. chimborazense* (Spruce) Christ, *D. condorensis* Pacheco & A.R.Sm., *D. corderoi* (Sodirol) Diels, *D. cristatum* (Desr.) Alston, *D. diplazioides* (Klotzsch & H.Karst.) Alston, *D. divisissimum* (Baker) Christ, *D. expansum* Willd., *D. ferulaceum* (T.Moore ex Hook.) Lellinger, *D. grandifolium* (Sw.) Sw., *D. hians* Kunze ex Klotzsch, *D. hieronymi* (Sodirol) C.Chr., *D. hyalinum* A.Rojas, *D. immensum* Stolze, *D. lanceolatum* A.Rojas, *D. lellingeri* Pacheco, *D. leptogrammoides* C.Chr., *D. lindbergii* (Mett.) Christ, *D. lonchophyllum* Kunze, *D. macrodictyon* (Baker) Diels, *D. macrophyllum* Desv., *D. mattogrossense* Samp., *D. melanosorum* (Sodirol) C.Chr., *D. mildei* (Kuhn) C.Chr., *D. moccennianum* (Sodirol) C.Chr., *D. moritzianum* Stolze, *D. myriomerum* (Christ) Lellinger, *D. navarretei* Stolze, *D. obscurum* Christ, *D. oellgaardii* Stolze, *D.*

ordinatum (Christ) Lellinger, *D. pactile* Lellinger, *D. palaviense* Stolze, *D. palmense* Rosenst., *D. paucipinnum* Stolze, *D. petiolulatum* (Stolze) A.R.Sm., *D. pinnatifidum* Kunze, *D. plantaginifolium* (L.) Urb., *D. prominulum* Maxon, *D. pseudocarnosum* A.Rojas, *D. pulicosum* (Hook.) T.Moore, *D. rivale* (Spruce) Diels, *D. robustum* (Sodirol) A.Rojas, *D. roemerianum* (Kunze) C.Presl, *D. rostratum* Fée, *D. sanctae-rosae* Christ, *D. sanderi* (C.Chr.) Pacheco, *D. seemannii* T.Moore, *D. sodiroanum* C.Chr., *D. sprucei* (Baker) C.Chr., *D. stolzei* (Pacheco & R.C.Moran) R.Kr.Singh, V.K.Rawat & Sanjeet Kumar, *D. striatastrum* Lellinger, *D. striatum* (L.) C.Presl, *D. stuebelianum* (Hieron.) Stolze, *D. stuebelii* Hieron, *D. subobtusum* Rosenst., *D. trianae* (Mett.) C.Chr., *D. tungurahuae* (Sodirol) C.Chr., *D. urticifolium* Christ, *D. vastum* (Mett.) Diels, *D. venulosum* (Baker) Diels, *D. vesiculosum* (Sodirol) C.Chr., *D. wilsonii* (Baker) Diels and *D. wolfii* Hieron., of which *D. angulosum* C.Chr., *D. condorensis* Pacheco & A.R.Sm., *D. corderoi* (Sodirol) Diels, *D. divisissimum* (Baker) Christ, *D. hieronymi* (Sodirol) C.Chr., *D. hyalinum* A.Rojas, *D. lanceolatum* A.Rojas, *D. lellingeri* Pacheco, *D. leptogrammoides* C.Chr., *D. melanosorum* (Sodirol) C.Chr., *D. mildei* (Kuhn) C.Chr., *D. navarretei* Stolze, *D. oellgaardii* Stolze, *D. sodiroanum* C.Chr., *D. stolzei* (Pacheco & R.C.Moran) R.Kr.Singh, V.K.Rawat & Sanjeet Kumar, *D. stuebelii* Hieron and *D. vesiculosum* (Sodirol) C.Chr. are endemic (POWO, 2025). However, the name *Callipteris stolzei* Pacheco & R.C.Moran needs to be transferred to the genus *Diplazium*, because in current circumscription *Callipteris* Bory is synonymous to *Diplazium* (Wei & Zhang, 2020). Therefore, a new combination is proposed here for *Callipteris stolzei* under the genus *Diplazium* as *D. stolzei* (Pacheco & R.C.Moran) R.Kr.Singh, V.K.Rawat & Sanjeet Kumar.

New combination

Diplazium stolzei (Pacheco & R.C.Moran) R.Kr.Singh, V.K.Rawat & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Callipteris stolzei* Pacheco & R.C.Moran, *Brittonia* 51(4): 381. 1999.

Holotype: Ecuador, Napo, Canton Archidona, Carretera Hollin-Loreto, Rio Huataraco, dos horas a pie desde la aldea de Guagua Sumaco, August 1989, C.E. Cerón & M. Factos 7436 (MO); isotypes MO, QCNE190!, UAMIZ.

Distribution: Endemic to Ecuador.

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